

Freshwater use of the energy sector in Africa

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Water use throughout the different stages of energy production in Africa is analysed.
- Important amounts of water are lost through evaporation in hydropower reservoirs.
- Fuelwood used in households is an important water consumer.
- The water use in thermal power plants depends highly on the type of cooling system.
- Non-hydro renewables are a good alternative for sustainable development in Africa.

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Water-energy nexus
Africa
Energy production
Hydropower
Power generation
Water for energy

ABSTRACT

The fast economic and population growth in the African continent will lead to an important increase in demand for energy and water resources. Unfortunately, very few studies have addressed water use for energy production in Africa. This study focuses on water consumption and withdrawals throughout the different stages of energy production (fuel production, power plant construction and operation) in African countries. An in-depth analysis of water loss through evaporation in hydropower reservoirs is also performed due to the important role it plays in many countries and its severe impacts on electricity generation during the increasingly frequent droughts in Africa. The results indicate that in the year 2016, a total of 42 billion cubic meters of water was lost through evaporation in hydropower reservoirs compared to 1.2 billion cubic meters from all the other fuel types combined. Oil extraction and refining dominate water use for fuel production and non-hydro renewable energies have an almost negligible impact on the overall water use (10 million cubic meters). Fuelwood is shown to be a high consumer of water accounting for 4.5 billion cubic meters. The use of non-hydro renewable energies instead of fossil fuels can contribute significantly to reduce water use while covering the growing energy needs in Africa. Modern technologies that substitute fuelwood use in households would also reduce the impacts on water resources. The hydropower potential remains largely untapped in several regions of the continent. Nevertheless, new hydropower developments need to be carefully considered especially in regions characterized by severe water scarcity.

1. Introduction

The energy sector is one of the largest consumers of water worldwide and in some developed and industrialized regions the highest consumer. In 2014, 10% of total water abstractions worldwide was used for energy production and power generation [1], reaching up to 40% in Europe [2] and the United States [3], mostly derived from freshwater resources. At the same time, water scarcity has become a serious

problem affecting many regions in the world. Longer and more intense droughts in larger areas have been observed since the 1970's specially in the tropics and sub-tropics, and future river run-off and water availability are expected to decrease by 10–30% in some dry regions [4]. Currently, around one fifth of the world's population live in water scarce regions and by 2025, two thirds of the world's population are expected to be living under water stress conditions [5].

Extensive research has been carried out to tackle the water used by

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115171>

Received 17 February 2020; Received in revised form 1 May 2020; Accepted 7 May 2020

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the energy sector. A number of studies have focused on estimating water intensity factors for the different processes involved in electricity production through systematic reviews and life cycle analyses [6–10]. Other studies have applied these water intensity factors to estimate the amount of water being used for energy and electricity production in different countries or regions [11–16]. When analysing the water use for energy production, it is important to make a distinction between withdrawal and consumption. Water withdrawal represent the water removed from the water body, while water consumption is the share of water withdrawal that is not returned to the water source, mainly water incorporated to crops or lost by evaporation [17]. These two terms differ significantly in many cases depending on the technology used. Fuel production, power plant construction and operation require important amounts of water depending on the extraction method or cooling technologies used. Coal needs to be washed after extraction and in some cases transported using slurry pipelines which is a highly water-intensive method. Natural gas and oil extraction are particularly dependent on water; water is used for drilling, refining and especially during hydraulic fracturing and enhanced oil recovery. Water is also used for extraction, processing and disposal of uranium especially during mining, milling and some enrichment processes [6,18].

Power plant operation, in particular cooling systems, also requires significant amounts of water, being in fact the largest use of water in the power plant life cycle for most of the technologies [6]. There are three main types of cooling systems: once-through systems, close-cycle systems and dry cooling systems. Each of these systems differs significantly in terms of water withdrawal and water consumption. The selection of the cooling system is subject to trade-offs mainly in terms of cost, environmental impacts and water use and thus it needs to be adapted to the different cooling requirements, location, climate or availability of water resources among others [19]. There is a tendency to switch from open-cycle cooling systems to wet cooling towers and dry cooling systems in the newly planned power plants despite the higher cost [20]. Some of the reasons include the high water requirements and the consequent higher vulnerability during droughts or heat waves but mainly the environmental impacts on the water bodies [21,22]

1.1. The African energy context

Energy demand in Africa accounts for only 6% of the global energy demand, regardless of representing 16% of the world's population. This situation is especially aggravated in Sub-Saharan Africa where more than two thirds of the population lack access to modern energy and around 620 million people do not have access to electricity. However, Africa shows the fastest population growth in the world. From 2000 to 2012, sub-Saharan population for instance increased by 270 million people and experienced an energy demand growth of 45% [23]. Africa's

total primary energy supply mix presents strong differences depending on the country or region. North Africa is greatly dependant on natural gas (50%) and oil (47%) while South Africa relies mainly on coal (70%). The situation in the rest of sub-Saharan Africa is radically different with a very strong presence of biomass and waste (76%) in the energy mix and smaller contributions from oil (16%), natural gas (4%) and other renewables (2.5%) [24]. The total primary energy supply and installed capacity by fuel type in Africa is shown in Fig. 1.

Future energy projections in Africa follow the increasing trends observed in the last few years and the continent is expected to experience the fastest energy demand growth in the world driven by population increase, urbanization and GDP growth [26]. In 2040, sub-Saharan Africa's population is expected to almost double and total primary energy demand is expected to increase by 80%. The power sector would quadruple its generation capacity, electricity demand more than triple and over 950 million people gain access to electricity [23]. This expected increase in energy production would imply more pressure on the African water resources and may intensify the competition with the agricultural sector. Currently, 86% of the water withdrawal in Africa is used for agriculture, 10% for municipal purposes and 4% for industry including energy [27].

Water scarcity affects many regions in Africa. Two thirds of the continent is arid or semi-arid and more than 300 million people living in sub-Saharan countries are affected by severe water shortages [28]. Africa covers 22% of the world's land but its share of renewable water resources is only 9%. Moreover, these water resources are unevenly distributed among countries or regions. North Africa, covering 15% of the African land, is the driest region with an average precipitation of 96 mm/year and a 1% share of the African renewable water resources. On the other hand, covering only 18% of the land, Central Africa possesses 48% of the renewable water resources of the continent [29]. These large intrinsic differences could be aggravated by changes in climate and precipitation patterns due to global warming. By 2080, precipitation is expected to increase by 22% in some regions and decrease by 33% in others [29]. More severe and longer droughts and floods and lower river flows in the dry seasons, could be some of the consequences in the already vast drylands of Africa [29].

1.2. Hydropower in Africa

Hydropower is one of the energy sources that are most affected by droughts and many African countries depend highly on it, especially in the Sub-Saharan region. In 2016, hydropower accounted for 54% of the installed capacity in Eastern Africa, 58% in Central Africa and 30% in Western Africa (not including Nigeria which relies on natural gas) with fourteen countries having a hydropower share above 50% and eight countries above 70% [25]. These highly hydropower-dependant

Fig. 1. Total primary energy supply and total installed capacity of power plants in Africa by fuel type in the year 2016 (data from [24,25]).

countries have faced important electricity cuts due to the lack of water caused by severe droughts [30–32]. On the other hand, hydropower generation can also be affected by floods which may cause a decrease of the dam capacity due to siltation and the need to increase the reserved flood safety margin [33].

The most important part of the overall water consumption from hydropower plants is the water lost through evaporation, which is directly related to the area of the reservoir. This consumption can be several times higher than the water consumption for fossil fuels or nuclear plants per unit of energy produced [10]. Seepage losses represent the second contributor to water consumption. However, water lost through seepage normally remains within the water basin while this is not the case for evaporated water, which represents a real loss [34].

Hydropower water loss has been analyzed from global to regional scale over the last two decades [29]. Applying water factors, as it is commonly done for other fuel types, is not an appropriate methodology in the case of hydropower due to the complexity of the variables that affect the link between energy production and evaporation in a hydropower plant. Water factors provided in the literature are characterized by a large variability [10,35] that would result in an excessive over- or under-estimation of the overall water loss. Previous studies of water consumption from hydropower have been carried out at a global scale [35–37] using reservoir data from global databases such as ICOLD [38] and GRaND [39] or based on case studies for which more accurate data of the reservoir areas may be available [40–42]. Global databases provide extensive data for a large number of reservoirs around the world. However, there are no details regarding the period where the areas have been measured or any information on their temporal evolution. Obtaining reservoir water surface data at satisfying spatial and temporal resolutions often represents an important challenge at a global scale when the number of reservoirs is large. Hydropower reservoir surfaces and volumes vary frequently over time due to regulation (storing, retaining and releasing water), region-specific climate (heat-waves, droughts, precipitation, wind speed, evaporation) and the number and intensity of shared uses [43,44].

The number of challenges that Africa presents in terms of energy-water nexus is significant. Furthermore, the lack of adequate management of available water resources is contributing to the water crisis in the African continent. Changes in climatic patterns are also expected to have impacts on crop yields [29], which in combination with population growth will lead to additional stress on water resources that would have to be dedicated to increase agricultural productivity. Under these scenarios, future water needs from the growing African energy sector may play a key role when combined with changes in water availability and future increasing demands from agriculture. Therefore, a proper analysis of the water requirements of the African energy sector is important for an effective future planning and management of water and energy resources in Africa.

The objective of this study is to develop reliable estimates of the energy sector's water consumption and withdrawal in the African countries including fuel extraction, processing, power plant construction and operation. As part of this objective and as a consequence of the highly important and challenging context of hydropower in Africa, an in-depth analysis of water loss through evaporation from hydropower plants is carried out. This analysis aims to tackle some of the challenges presented in terms of spatial resolution and temporal evolution when targeting a large number of reservoirs by using high-resolution water extents on a monthly basis at the continental scale in Africa.

2. Data and methodology

The energy sector's water requirements vary considerably depending on the types of cooling systems, fuel extraction methods, plant location or climatic conditions [6]. In this section, the different processes involved in energy production are analysed separately, rather

than as steps of the electricity lifecycle like in other similar studies in the literature [6,13,14]. The reason for this is that the electricity life cycle involves the fuel life cycle, which at the same time includes fuel production (locally produced or imported), capacity factors and the thermal efficiency of the power plant. This approach would account for virtual water via imported fuels (accounting virtual water is avoided when possible throughout the study), and it would be difficult to have a clear idea of the real water used for fuel production due to the effect of the thermal efficiency (higher water use per unit of electricity generated than per fuel unit). A separate analysis of the water use for fuel extraction also avoids transferring the potential errors in the capacity factors of the power plants (which may be important due to poor data availability in Africa) to the water use of the fuel cycle.

The processes analysed in this study are fuel production, power plant construction and power plant operation for non-hydro plants. A separate section is dedicated to hydropower. The year 2016 has been selected as the study year since it is the most complete in terms of data for all the sources used. Details on the specific stages and boundaries considered within each process are detailed in their respective sections.

2.1. Fuel production

Fuel production data at country level in Africa is gathered from different sources. Coal, crude oil and natural gas production, imports, exports and total primary energy supply are collected from IEA [24] and AFREC [45] statistics. Regarding oil extraction, only onshore production is taken into account since offshore oil fields use seawater for the extraction. The percentages of onshore/offshore oil production per country are inferred from [46]. The percentage of the water produced in oil wells that is reinjected is not considered as water consumption and therefore, the water factors take into account only the extra water needed for the extraction. The water produced-to-oil extracted ratios and the percentages of reinjection are estimated based on data from different oil producing regions in the United States due to the lack of specific African data [47].

Data on Uranium production is collected from the World Nuclear Association [48] which provides yearly production for each mine of the three uranium producers in Africa: Namibia, Niger and South Africa. Enrichment, fuel fabrication, storage and disposal of nuclear fuel do not take place in Africa, therefore this study only considers water use during extraction and milling. No information was found about the nature of the water used for oil extraction and uranium mining, therefore water withdrawal is considered equal to consumption in these two cases. Table 1 summarizes the water factors used for each fuel type as well as the data sources.

The water use of fuel production is therefore calculated using the following equation:

$$WFP_{ij} \text{ (m}^3\text{)} = \text{Fuel produced}_{ij} \text{ (MWhf)} * \text{Fuel water factor}_{ij} \text{ (m}^3\text{/MWhf)} \quad (1)$$

where WFP is the water use for fuel production and the subscripts i and j represent the country and fuel type respectively.

No consistent or relevant information on biofuel production in Africa aside from fuelwood was found, therefore, in this study only water use for fuelwood is analysed. Fuelwood production and consumption data for different uses in Africa are collected from UN data [51]. Water factors for roundwood production are obtained from [52] and are summarized in Table 2. These factors are calculated taking into account the evapotranspiration and the relative value of roundwood production compared to other forest ecosystem services in different climatic regions [52].

2.2. Power plant operation

Most of the water used during power plant operation belongs to

Table 1

Water consumption and withdrawal factors for the different processes involved in fuel extraction and processing of coal, crude oil, natural gas and uranium.

Fuel	Processes	Consumption (m ³ /MWhf) ^a			Withdrawal (m ³ /MWhf) ^a			Source
		Median	Min	Max	Median	Min	Max	
Coal	Extraction and processing ^b	0.0523	0.0154	0.1916	0.0529	0.0154	0.1916	[6]
Crude oil	Extraction (first and secondary recovery) ^c	0.2011	0	0.5271	0.2011	0	0.5271	[34,47]
	Refining	0.1710	0.0988	0.1828	0.1710	0.0988	0.1828	[34,47]
Natural gas	Extraction and processing ^d	0.0019	0	0.0386	0.0019	0	0.0405	[6]
Uranium ^e	Surface mining and milling	0.0059	0.0005	0.0083	0.0059	0.0005	0.0083	[6,49,50]
	Underground mining and milling	0.0028	0.0002	0.0184	0.0028	0.0002	0.0184	[6,49,50]

^a Water factors for coal, natural gas and uranium extraction provided by [6] are expressed as m³/MWh_e (electric) and are converted to m³/MWh_f (fuel) by removing the corresponding harmonization parameters used by the authors.

^b Calculated as the average of the water factors for surface and underground mining due to lack of information regarding the mining method used in the coal production data sources following [14].

^c Calculated as the weighted average (based on US production) of first and secondary recovery due to lack of information on the oil extraction methods used in each African country following [14].

^d Includes conventional natural gas extraction and processing.

^e For Namibia, the water consumption in the two main uranium mines is provided by the yearly mining reports [49,50] while for the third uranium mine in the country, an average of the water intensity factors of the other two is applied. The water factors in the table are applied in Niger and South Africa and are obtained from an average of the water consumption from the Namibian mines in combination with data from [6].

cooling systems in thermoelectric technologies. In order to estimate the water use for power plant operation in Africa, a comprehensive dataset of the African power plants is required, in combination with water factors for each type of power plant and cooling system. PLATTS database [25] provides a detailed dataset at country level of the power plants in Africa with specific information on the fuel type, installed capacity, cooling system, generation technology used, etc. However, information regarding the type of cooling system is missing for 66% of the steam turbine-based thermoelectric power plants. Part of the missing information is completed based on aerial images of the power plants [53]. In the few cases where this approach was not possible, the same type of cooling system installed in similar power plants in the same country or region is assumed. If no reasonable reference was available, average values of consumption and withdrawal factors of the most commonly used cooling technologies in the country or region are applied. Since PLATTS does not provide the exact location of the power plants, the coordinates are obtained from other power plant databases [54–56]. The location of the power plants is important to determine the type of water used for cooling (freshwater or saltwater) since plants located near the coast tend to use seawater for this purpose. In some cases, the type of water used is reported by PLATTS, however, in many other cases it is not specified. The power plants that use saltwater as reported by PLATTS are not taken into account in the operational water calculations since the target of this study is freshwater use. For the rest of the plants without information on the type of water used, saltwater is assumed when the location is within 5 km from the coast, and therefore, these plants are also removed from the operational water calculations. Exceptions to this are PV plants and wind turbines, for which the operational water is mainly used for cleaning purposes and therefore freshwater is considered. For simplicity, and since we address only freshwater use, from this point and throughout the study, any mention of water use will be referring to freshwater.

Table 2

Water consumption factors for fuelwood production in different regions of Africa according to the climate zone.

Source: [52].

Climate zone		Water consumption (m ³ water/m ³ roundwood) ^a	Blue water consumption (m ³ water/m ³ roundwood) ^b
North Africa	Subtropics, summer rainfall	65	2
South Africa	Subtropics, winter rainfall	57	2
Rest of Africa	Tropical	93	4

^a Estimated as water lost by evaporation and retained as moisture content in the harvested wood.

^b Blue water represents the fraction of water consumption that originates from capillary rise. Green water is the part of water consumption that is not blue water [52].

While the installed capacity of each power plant is provided by PLATTS, no information is given on the actual electricity output. In order to estimate the annual electricity production for each power plant, the capacity factors at country level for each type of plant are calculated based on data from IRENA [57], IEA [24] and UN [51] using the following equation:

$$CF_{ij} = (Total\ generation_{ij} (MWh)) / (Installed\ capacity_{ij} (MW) * 24 * 365) \tag{2}$$

And therefore, the electricity generated by each power plant is obtained from:

$$Electricity\ generated_k (MWh) = CF_{ij} * Installed\ capacity_k (MW) \tag{3}$$

where the subscript *k* refers to the power plant and *CF_{ij}* is the capacity factor corresponding to the country and fuel type where the power plant *k* is located. The *Total generation* is the summation of the *Electricity generated* for all the power plants in a given country and for a given type of fuel.

Consumption and withdrawal water factors for the different power plant types and cooling systems are summarized in Table 3, covering the technologies present in the African power plants for the target year of 2016.

Once the annual electricity output is calculated and the water factors are established, the water consumption and withdrawal can be calculated using the following equation:

$$WOP_{ij} (m^3) = \sum_k^n Electricity\ generated_k (MWh) * WF_{jc} (m^3/MWh) \tag{4}$$

where *WOP* is the water use for power plant operation, *WF* the water factor, *n* the number of power plants in each country for each fuel type and the subscript *c* is the cooling system/power plant technology type according to Table 3.

Table 3

Water consumption and withdrawal factors for power plant operation based on fuel type, cooling system and technology used in the power plants, including data sources.

Fuel	Cooling system	Technology type	Consumption (m ³ /MWh)			Withdrawal (m ³ /MWh)			Source
			Median	Min	Max	Median	Min	Max	
Coal	CT	SUB	2.008	0.758	4.924	2.500	1.742	4.545	[6]
	Dry	SUB	0.417	0.250	0.591	0.367	0.252	0.517	[58]
	Dry	SUP	0.322	0.211	0.456	0.322	0.211	0.456	[58]
Natural gas/Oil/Waste heat ^a	OT	SUB/SUP ^b	1.098	0.720	1.553	136.364	132.576	140.152	[6]
	OT	CC	0.379	0.076	0.871	34.091	27.273	79.545	[6]
	CT	SUB	2.765	2.121	4.167	4.545	4.545	4.545	[6]
	CT	CC	0.795	0.178	1.136	0.947	0.568	2.879	[6]
	Dry	CC	0.015	0.015	0.455	0.015	0.000	0.015	[6]
	Dry ^c	SUB	0.417	0.250	0.591	0.367	0.252	0.517	[58]
	N/A	GT/IC ^d	0.189	0.189	1.288	1.629	1.629	1.629	[6]
Nuclear	OT	SUB	1.515	0.379	1.515	178.030	87.121	227.273	[6]
	CT	SUB ^e	0.042	0.019	1.364	0.068	0.042	0.095	[6]
	Dry	SUB ^{e,f}	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	[10]
Geothermal	Dry	ORC ^g	1.098	1.023	2.386	1.098	1.023	2.386	[6]
	CT	SUB	2.095	1.818	3.655	3.326	1.894	5.530	[10]
Biomass	OT	SUB	1.136	1.136	1.136	132.576	75.758	189.394	[10]
	N/A	GT/IC ^d	0.189	0.189	1.288	1.629	1.629	1.629	[6]
	CT	Fresnel	3.788	3.788	3.788	3.788	3.788	3.788	[6]
Solar	CT	Trough	3.371	2.121	7.197	3.636	3.295	4.167	[6]
	Dry	Power tower	0.098	0.098	0.098	0.098	0.098	0.098	[6]
	Dry	Trough	0.295	0.121	0.530	0.295	0.125	0.299	[6]
	N/A	PV	0.023	0.004	0.098	0.023	0.004	0.098	[6]
	Wind	N/A	Wind turbine	0.001	0.000	0.008	0.004	0.004	0.004

OT: Once-through, CT: cooling tower, SUB: steam turbine subcritical, SUP: steam turbine supercritical, GT: gas turbine, IC: internal combustion engine, CC: combined cycle, ORC: Organic Rankine Cycle.

^a The water factors of natural gas power plants are applied to oil and waste heat power plants due to data limitations, following [14,59].

^b Ref. [6] does not differentiate between subcritical and supercritical steam turbines, therefore the same value is applied in both cases.

^c The water factors of “Coal-Dry Cooling- SUBCR” are applied due to the lack of specific values for natural gas.

^d Due to lack of data, the water factors of GT provided by [6] are applied to IC since both technologies present the similarity of requiring no water for cooling.

^e Ref. [25] does not provide the type of technology used, therefore the water factors of flash technology are used since it is the most commonly used technology in geothermal plants.

^f Due to data limitations it is assumed that withdrawal and consumption are equal.

^g Rankine cycle is the commercial binary cycle used in the United States, therefore and due to data limitations, the water factors of binary power plants in [6] are applied.

2.3. Power plant construction

Water use for power plant construction is negligible in most thermoelectric technologies (except for CSP plants) compared to water use during power plant operation. Other non-thermoelectric renewable technologies included in this study (PV and wind) use instead larger amounts of water during power plant construction than during operation [6]. Power plant construction may involve virtual water through imported components of the power plant (e.g.: steam turbines, solar panels, etc.) that is difficult to separate from the local water use. The water factors used for the calculations are included in Table 4. The water use for power plant construction is obtained similarly to the water use for operation using the equivalent of Eq. (4).

2.4. Hydropower

In this section the gross water lost through evaporation in the African hydropower reservoirs is analysed. Water loss through seepage is not addressed since as previously referred it normally remains within the water basin and evaporation is the main contributor to the reservoir water loss.

The Global Surface Water (GSW) dataset developed by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (JRC) [62] provides a consistent monthly water history (MWH) [63] and a yearly water classification history (YC) [64] of the extent of water bodies at global scale. The dataset covers the period from March 1984 to December 2018 (418 months, updated annually), and it is derived from Landsat imagery at 30 m resolution. For this analysis, GSW data for the

reference period 2000–2018 is used, with a particular focus on the year 2016 as the reference year for the study.

The reference extent of a reservoir in this study is represented by the area of the GSW within the Maximum Water Extent (MWE) between the start and end point of the water accumulation. The MWE is the area where water has been detected at least once during the full time series [62]. A reservoir's end point is characterized by the site for water discharge control (usually the dam), while the reservoir starting point is located where the influence of the water accumulation caused by the presence of the hydropower plant begins. Some run-off-the-river plants are also considered in those cases where the stations' structure create an impoundment detected using remote sensing techniques.

In order to analyse the seasonal variation of the water extents, the start and end of the wet and dry seasons need to be defined. The start and end month of the wet season is obtained from daily rainy season estimates from [65] at each reservoir centroid. All months outside the rainy season are assigned to the dry season. Eq. (5) presents the rainy season precipitation based on CHIRPS (The Climate Hazard InfraRed Precipitation with Stations) [66] daily precipitation at 5 km spatial resolution averaged for the period 1981 to 2017:

$$M_i = \sum_{d=-14}^{15} P_{i+d} \tag{5}$$

where M_i is the 30-day precipitation moving sum around the i^{th} day and P_i is the daily precipitation value at the i^{th} day. The i^{th} day belongs to the rainy season of a specific year if M_i is greater than 100 mm or the annual 50th percentile of the M_i of the same year. An end day of rainy season greater than 366 means that the rainy season goes beyond

Table 4

Water consumption and withdrawal factors for power plant construction for different fuel types and technologies used in the power plants.

Fuel	Technology type	Consumption (m ³ /MWh)			Withdrawal (m ³ /MWh)		
		Median	Min	Max	Median	Min	Max
Coal	ST	0.0039	0.0012	0.0986	0.0039	0.0012	0.0473
Oil ^a	ST	0.0058	0.0017	0.0058	0.0058	0.0017	0.0058
	GT	0.0077	0.0023	0.0077	0.0077	0.0023	0.0077
	IC	0.0058	0.0018	0.0058	0.0058	0.0018	0.0058
	CC	0.0056	0.0017	0.0056	0.0056	0.0017	0.0056
Natural gas	ST	0.0059	0.0018	0.0059	0.0059	0.0018	0.0059
	GT	0.0063	0.0019	0.0063	0.0063	0.0019	0.0063
	IC	0.0052	0.0016	0.0052	0.0052	0.0016	0.0052
	CC	0.0043	0.0013	0.0043	0.0043	0.0013	0.0043
Nuclear	ST	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007
Geothermal	ST	0.0076	0.0076	0.0076	0.0114	0.0011	0.0379
Solar	PV ^b	0.2896	0.0367	0.7488	0.3386	0.0036	6.0112
	CSP	0.6057	0.3028	0.6435	0.6057	0.3748	0.6435
Wind		0.0038	0.0004	0.0341	0.0984	0.0492	0.3142
Hydropower		0.0011	0.0011	0.0011	0.0011	0.0011	0.0011
Waste heat/gas ^a	ST	0.0059	0.0018	0.0059	0.0018	0.0018	0.0059
	IC	0.0052	0.0016	0.0052	0.0016	0.0016	0.0052
Biomass ^c	ST	0.0039	0.0012	0.0986	0.0039	0.0012	0.0473
	GT	0.0039	0.0012	0.0986	0.0039	0.0012	0.0473
	IC	0.0039	0.0012	0.0986	0.0039	0.0012	0.0473

ST: steam turbine, GT: gas turbine, IC: internal combustion engine, CC: combined cycle, CSP: concentrated solar power.

Source: water factors obtained from [6] in combination with thermal efficiencies from EIA [60].

^a Following [14,59], and due to lack of specific data, the water factors for natural gas from [6] are used also for oil. Specific thermal efficiencies for the different technology types of oil power plants from EIA [60] are then applied resulting in the water factors of the table.

^b A weighted average of crystalline-silicone and thin-film are applied (94% crystalline-silicone and 6% others) based on [61].

^c Due to lack of data, water factors are assumed the same as for coal.

December into the following Gregorian year [65]. If a reservoir is located in a region characterized by a persistent dry or wet season, only that specific season is considered.

For each reservoir, monthly information about water, land and no-data areas and their ratios within the MWE (1984–2018) is derived from the GSW Monthly Water History (MWH) for the period 2000 to 2018, using Google Earth Engine [67]. Seasonal (dry and wet) and annual aggregations of reservoir's water areas are obtained from the GSW-MWH and from the GSW-YC [62]. Only months and years with less or equal 10% no-data coverage within the MWE are taken into account. In case the commissioning date of the dam was 2000 or later, the year after the commissioning year is set as start date for the analysis, assuming the reservoir reached its standard operational water level at that time.

Information on African hydropower plants is gathered from PLATTS [25]. The hydropower plants are included in the study if (i) the location of the plant can clearly be identified, (ii) the installed capacity is greater or equal to 5 MW (due to very limited availability of location data for smaller plants) and (iii) the reservoir shows artificial water accumulation by comparing GSW data, Google Earth [53] and OpenStreetMaps [68]. The final selection of power plants according to these criteria results in 159 plants. The location of the plants is obtained from a combination of sources [54–56] and cross-checked with maps and aerial satellite images from Google Earth [53], OpenStreetMaps [68] and the MWE of the GSW [62] to ensure accuracy. The total number of operational hydropower plants in Africa in 2016 is 529 with a total installed capacity of 30.2GW. The 159 plants analysed in this study cover 95% of this capacity and therefore can be considered as a good representation of the hydropower fleet in the continent.

The potential evaporation (E_v) from reservoir water surfaces is obtained by applying the FAO methodology for open water surfaces expressed by Eq. (6) [69].

$$ET_c = ET_o * K_c \quad (6)$$

where ET_c is the crop evapotranspiration (mm), ET_o the reference evapotranspiration (mm) and K_c the crop coefficient.

This methodology assumes no transpiration and a crop coefficient of 1 for open water, resulting in Eq. (7). The reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) is calculated using the LISVAP model [70,71]. Temperature, wind speed, relative humidity and solar radiation data at 30 km spatial resolution are collected from ERA5 [72] and used as input together with the areas of the reservoirs for the year 2016. Two seasonal and one annual (2016) ET_o values are obtained aggregating the individual grid-cells corresponding to each reservoir.

$$E_v = ET_o * A * 10^{-3} \quad (7)$$

where E_v is the evaporation in the reservoir (m³) and A the reservoir's area (m²).

The last aspect to take into account is the allocation of water use to other beneficiaries and eco-system services such as irrigation, water supply, fishing, navigation, flood control and recreation. Ignoring the multi-purpose aspect of a reservoir would lead to an overestimation of the hydropower water consumption. Information regarding the uses of the reservoirs is gathered from GRanD [39], ICOLD [38] and FAO [73] databases. The allocation of uses in multipurpose reservoirs is one of the most challenging points when analysing evaporation water losses and there is not a scientifically accepted methodology [74]. In this study a ranking-based allocation is selected. Full allocation to hydropower is assigned to reservoirs for which the first use is electricity generation. If hydropower is not the primary use of the reservoir, a corresponding weight is given according to the rank of hydropower production among competing reservoir uses: 50% for secondary use, 33% for tertiary use, etc. [13]. If no information is available in any of the three databases (14% of the reservoirs analysed), satellite images and online sources are used to find further details. In a few cases when online sources do not provide enough information of the use for hydropower, a minimum allocation of 10% is assigned for electricity generation in the reservoir. This is considered since we assume as valid the information provided in PLATTS where there is a clear indication of the presence of a hydroelectric power plant in those reservoirs.

Fig. 2. Distribution of power plants in Africa by fuel type (fossil fuels, renewable energies, nuclear energy and waste heat) indicated by the colours and installed capacity indicated by the size of the circles (data from [25,54–56]).

3. Results

The water use for different stages of energy production and fuel types is estimated for the African countries and the results are presented in this section. Sections 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 are dedicated to each of the energy production stages (fuel production, power plant operation and construction) for all fuel types except for hydropower and fuelwood which are presented in separate subsections due to their particularities. Section 3.4 presents a summary of the total water use from the three previous subsections. Section 3.5 is dedicated to water use for fuelwood and Section 3.6 includes the results for hydropower and an in-depth analysis of other non-hydro renewables, which are normally overshadowed by the high water use of the other energy types. Fig. 2 presents the spatial distribution of the power plants that are considered in this study classified by fuel type and installed capacity.

3.1. Water use for fuel production

The total water consumption for fuel production in Africa in 2016 is estimated at 728 mcm, corresponding to coal, oil, natural gas and uranium extraction and processing according to the different processes indicated in Table 1. The water consumption for fuel production is

clearly dominated by oil with the highest water factors (for extraction and refining) among all fuel types. While oil accounts for 48% of the total fuel production in Africa in energy content, oil extraction and refining represent 86% of the total water consumption for primary fuel production in the continent. Out of this water consumption, 53% belongs to oil extraction and 33% to oil refining. The remaining water consumption is shared between coal (13%, belonging mainly to South Africa) and natural gas and uranium (2%). Furthermore, natural gas, despite being the second in terms of fuel production after oil, has a water consumption of only 1% due to a less water-intensive extraction process than oil. Fig. 3 shows the water consumption for fuel production for the 20 countries with the highest values. Algeria, South Africa, Egypt, Nigeria and Libya lead the list of countries with higher consumption, all based on oil and gas except for South Africa (based on coal). Other countries with important oil production (e.g.: Angola, Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Ghana and Cameroon), have however small water consumption due to the higher presence of offshore wells. For the majority of African countries, oil represents the highest share in water consumption, with the exception of South Africa, Mozambique, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Tanzania, Swaziland and Malawi with more water associated to coal production and Namibia to uranium production. Uranium extraction is only present in three countries in Africa and

Fig. 3. Water consumption for extraction (fossil fuels and uranium) and oil refining for the top 20 countries with the highest water values. Enlarged detailed view presented for 15 countries due to the large disparities in scale existing among the African countries.

overall the impact on water use is not significant compared to other fuel types. Namibia is the highest producer of uranium in Africa followed very closely by Niger, dedicating 4.7 mcm and 2.5 mcm of water respectively to uranium extraction. Water withdrawal for fuel production is not depicted due to the fact that the water factors for consumption and withdrawal are considered equal in many cases and therefore the results would be similar.

3.2. Water use for power plant operation

The total installed capacity in Africa in the year 2016 is 196 GW according to [25]. Natural gas power plants dominate due to the strong influence of Northern African countries and Nigeria in Western Africa representing 37% of the total installed capacity. They are followed by coal with 23% (deriving mainly from the effect of South Africa), oil (16%), hydropower (15%) and other energy types including renewable energies, waste heat and nuclear (9%) (see Fig. 1).

The total water consumption and withdrawal for power plant operation in Africa are estimated at 502 and 5418 mcm respectively. Figs. 4, 5 and 6 depict the water consumption and withdrawal for power plant operation in the African countries by fuel type. Cooling of fossil fuel power plants has a clear dominance covering a total of 96% and 91% share of the total water consumption and withdrawal respectively. While natural gas is the fuel with the highest installed capacity among power plants in Africa, it only contributes 15% to the total water consumption for power plant operation, accounting however for 67% to the water withdrawal. This relatively small consumption compared to other fuel types is mostly caused by the high installed capacity of natural gas power plants with gas turbines and open-cycle cooling systems (technologies characterized by smaller water

Fig. 5. Water consumption for power plant operation by fuel type for the top 20 countries with the highest water values. Enlarged detailed view presented for the last 18 countries due to scale difference.

Fig. 6. Water withdrawal for power plant operation by fuel type for the top 20 countries with the highest water values. Enlarged detailed view presented for the last 16 countries due to scale difference.

consumptions) in the top five gas-fired power producers in Africa (i.e., Egypt, Algeria, Nigeria, Libya and Tunisia). On the contrary, the use of this cooling technology becomes the main reason for the high water withdrawal associated to natural gas power plants, with Egypt being the topmost contributor due to its higher number of power plants using this type of cooling system. Coal power plants, on the other hand, show the opposite behaviour to the one described for natural gas. Water consumption becomes very high (77%) while water withdrawal is minimal (9%) in comparison, a situation mainly driven by South Africa. Such high consumption and small withdrawal are a consequence of the more generalized use of wet cooling towers in South African coal power plants. The third energy source after natural gas and coal in terms of installed capacity in Africa is oil. Oil power plants are the most

Fig. 4. Water consumption and withdrawal for power plant operation for different fuel types, aggregated for the whole African continent.

numerous among the thermal power plants in the continent, and only after hydroelectric plants among all types. However, the large majority of these plants are based on internal combustion engines with small installed capacities, thus covering only 16% of the total installed capacity in the continent. Oil-fired electricity generation has been generally declining with time. In Africa, the existing oil-based steam turbine plants are only located in countries with high installed capacities. Oil-fired gas turbines seem to follow a similar behaviour, although their presence is slightly higher. On the other hand, small internal combustion engines appear to be the technology commonly chosen when using oil to produce electricity, especially by countries with small installed capacities, covering fully the oil-fired electricity generation in most of the cases. It is important to notice that not only the number of plants is high, but these types of plants are also present in almost all African countries. Oil power plants contribute with a relatively strong presence in water withdrawal due to a higher use of open-cycle cooling systems compared to close-cycle systems in the steam turbine-based power plants. Egypt, Morocco and Sudan are the top three countries with the highest water withdrawal caused by cooling. These countries possess oil power plants equipped with open-cycle cooling systems or steam turbines with other cooling systems using freshwater. On the other hand, some of the countries with the highest installed oil power plant capacities have instead small water consumption and withdrawal. This is due to the use of seawater for cooling or the presence of gas turbines in some of the biggest plants of these countries. This is the case of Libya, South Africa, Nigeria and Tunisia for instance. Waste heat power plants refer mainly to power plants using steam turbines on combined cycle. Most of the biggest plants of this type are equipped with open-cycle cooling systems which are the reason of a stronger share in the water withdrawal compared to consumption, especially in Egypt.

Non-hydro renewable energies (i.e., solar, biomass, geothermal and wind) have the lowest operational water use among all types of energies covering less than 2% of the total water consumption and less than 1% of water withdrawal (Figs. 5 and 6). One of the reasons is the small installed capacity compared to fossil fuel power plants in Africa (4% vs 75%). However, in the case of geothermal, solar PV and wind, the water factors are also much lower compared to other types of energies (for instance PV and wind only use water for cleaning purposes). In these cases, a wider installation of these technologies is not expected to

Fig. 8. Water consumption for power plant construction by fuel type for the top 20 countries with the highest water values. Enlarged detailed view presented for the last 14 countries due to scale difference.

increase notably the water use. This is not the case of CSP plants which have considerably high water factors due to cooling even compared to fossil fuels based power plants.

3.3. Water use for power plant construction

Water use for power plant construction is the smallest term among the three analysed in this study, with a total of 4.5 mcm and 5.5 mcm for consumption and withdrawal respectively. In this case, renewable energies have a more significant contribution to the water use, especially regarding withdrawal which accounts for 43% of the total, following fossil fuels (56%) very closely. Water consumption is not small either, with 31% of the total compared to 69% by fossil fuels (Fig. 7). Solar plants, especially those using PV technologies, are the highest contributors within renewable energies with 29% and 27% of the water consumption and withdrawal respectively followed by wind energy. South Africa leads the list of countries with the highest water use (both consumption and withdrawal) due to coal and solar power plants followed by Northern African countries with natural gas, oil and solar plants as maximum contributors (Figs. 8 and 9).

Fig. 7. Water consumption and withdrawal for power plant construction for different fuel types, aggregated for the whole African continent.

Fig. 9. Water withdrawal for power plant construction by fuel type for the top 20 countries with the highest water values. Enlarged detailed view presented for the last 13 countries due to scale difference.

3.4. Total water use for non-hydro energies

The total water consumption and withdrawal for non-hydro energies calculated as the sum of water for fuel extraction, power plant

operation and construction are estimated at 1235 mcm and 6152 mcm respectively. Although the installed capacity of oil power plants is the smallest among all fossil fuels in Africa, oil extraction and refining are highly water-intensive processes that set oil as the highest water consumer overall. Coal becomes the second in terms of water consumption due to cooling of South African power plants. On the other end, natural gas appears as the lowest water consumer caused by a very small water use during extraction and the use of less water consumptive technologies to generate electricity such as gas turbines and steam turbines with open-cycle cooling systems. Regarding water withdrawal, natural gas is in this case the responsible of more than half of the total amount caused by cooling of power plants equipped with open-cycle systems. It is followed by oil due to the extraction and refining processes. Renewable energies have overall a very small water use covering all combined less than 1% of the total for both consumption and withdrawal. Figs. 10 and 11 present the distribution of the water use by different fuel types per country while Fig. 12 provides a number of energy and water variables aggregated for the five regions in Africa.

Fig. 10. Total water consumption (fuel production, power plant construction and operation) for different fuel types (fossil fuels, non-hydro renewables, nuclear and waste heat). The bar diagrams present the countries with the highest water use within the five African regions. Disparities in the amount of water use within the countries are shown in the map with a scale that allows to visualize also some details of countries with less water use.

Fig. 11. Total water withdrawal (fuel production, power plant construction and operation) for different fuel types (fossil fuels, renewables, nuclear and waste heat). The bar diagrams present the countries with the highest water use within the five African regions. Disparities in the amount of water use within the countries are shown in the map with a scale that allows to visualize also some details of countries with less water use.

Fig. 12. Energy and water use summary at continental scale and for each African region. “Installed capacity” column: the map presents the sum of installed capacity for all fuel types for each country and the circular diagrams indicate the share of each fuel type in the total installed capacity of the region. “Fuel production” column: the diagrams in “total production” present the share of each fuel type in the total fuel production of the region and the diagrams in “water consumption” show the share per fuel type of water consumption for the production of these fuels. “Power plant operation” column: the diagrams in “water consumption” present the share of each fuel type in the total water consumption for power plant operation in the region and the diagrams in “water withdrawal” show the share of each fuel type in the total water withdrawal for power plant operation in the region.

3.5. Water consumption for fuelwood

Green water (precipitation) and blue water (groundwater through capillary rise) consumption for fuelwood production in Africa are estimated in 103,820 mcm and 4579 mcm respectively. Fig. 13 depicts the amounts of green and blue water used for fuelwood production at country level distributed by sectors. The latest data available on energy access in Africa in 2015 [75] indicates that 66% of the population relies on biomass for cooking, reaching values of more than 80% in 22 countries. As a consequence of this and in line with the results shown in Fig. 13, the main water use associated to fuelwood consumption belongs to households, covering more than half of the total water consumption.

Fig. 13. Water consumption for fuelwood production for the top 20 countries with the highest water values and the share for different final uses. The distinction between green and blue water is indicated by the dashed line, being the blue water, the share corresponding to the upper part.

3.6. Water use for renewable energies

In the year 2016, the total installed capacity of renewable energies (hydropower, wind, solar, biomass and geothermal power) in Africa was 38 GW as opposed to 157 GW for fossil fuels and nuclear power plants. Hydropower had a clear dominance covering 79% of renewable energies. It represents, however, a smaller share of 15% among all types of energies.

3.6.1. Non-hydro renewable energies

The total water consumption for power plant operation and construction associated to non-hydro renewable energies is estimated in 10 mcm. In the case of withdrawal, the amount almost doubles reaching 18.3 mcm. The biggest share belongs to biomass, with 60% and 71% of the water

consumption and withdrawal due to cooling of steam turbines. Wind energy occupies the second position in terms of installed capacity of renewable energy in Africa after hydropower. However, both total water consumption and withdrawal are the smallest among all types of energies. This is caused by very small operational water factors only comparable to dry cooling in geothermal power plants. Within the solar technologies (PV and CSP), CSP is generally more water intensive than PV both for consumption and withdrawal. While operations of PV plants only require water for cleaning purposes, CSP power plants have a higher water use due to their cooling requirements. In the case of PV plants, most of the water is used during the construction phase. Although the water factors for CSP construction are still much higher (requiring twice more water) than for PV technologies, the total water use during this stage results significantly smaller than for PV due

to a much lower installed CSP capacity (364.6 MW) compared to PV (2058.6 MW). Fig. 14 illustrates the total water use in Africa during the construction and operational phase for the different types of renewable energies.

3.6.2. Hydropower

The total water loss through evaporation allocated to hydropower production in Africa in the year 2016 is estimated at 42,239 mcm. The five countries with the highest contribution are Ghana, Egypt, Zambia, Mozambique and Zimbabwe. In these countries are located the four biggest reservoirs in the continent (i.e., Akosombo, Aswan, Kariba and Cahora Bassa. Fig. 15) covering an area of 17954 km² and which account for almost two thirds of the total water loss. Table 5 presents the 36 countries with hydropower reservoirs analysed in the study including also information on

Fig. 14. Water consumption and withdrawal for renewable energies (biomass, solar, geothermal and wind) during the construction and operational phase for the whole African continent. The circular diagram represents the aggregation of all energy types for these two phases. Solar energy aggregates CSP and PV technologies, presented also separately to show their differences in the distribution of water use.

Fig. 15. Map with the location of the hydropower plants analysed in the study including information on the size of the reservoir and water loss/energy production of the associated power plant. Major rivers and lakes are represented and grey/white areas indicate the length of the wet season.

the total installed capacity, electricity production, number of reservoirs, areas covered and water loss per unit of energy production. Water consumption aggregated for all non-hydro energy types are also presented in Table 5 for comparison (as presented in Fig. 10). The results indicate that the amount of water loss by evaporation from reservoirs is in most cases several orders of magnitude larger than the total water consumption by all other types of fuels combined. Among the countries with the highest water loss due to evaporation, Ghana for instance loses 2322 times more water in hydropower reservoirs than in energy production from all other fuel types combined. In the case of Egypt, hydropower is a secondary use in Aswan dam, and its hydropower installed capacity is only 2.7 GW compared to 36GW for the rest of the power plants in the country. However, the water loss allocated to hydropower is still 33 times higher than the water used for all other fuel types combined.

Fig. 16 presents results on the water loss through evaporation allocated to hydropower and the installed capacity of the hydropower plants considered in this study. Egypt, Zambia, Mozambique, Ghana and Zimbabwe are the countries with the highest water loss through evaporation compared to their hydropower installed capacities, mainly caused by the large areas

covered by their reservoirs. On the other hand, countries like South Africa, Ethiopia, Morocco, Congo D.R. or Angola have relatively small water losses compared to their hydropower installed capacity. In these cases, the areas of the reservoirs are relatively small compared to other countries with similar installed capacities, which causes smaller evaporation losses. The accumulation of small hydropower reservoirs in these regions can be observed in Fig. 15. South Africa and Morocco for instance count with a large number of reservoirs of small size but important installed capacities all combined. However, in the case of Morocco, the electricity produced is three times smaller compared to Congo D.R. which has a smaller installed capacity and similar reservoir areas, probably caused by less water to run the turbines due to a drier climate. Reservoir's surface and evaporation rate are the two variables that affect the water loss (see Eq. (7)). As it has been discussed for Fig. 16, for similar installed capacities, depending on the size of the reservoir we may have very different water losses. The climate of the region through the evaporation rate is also important, however, the effect is not directly visible in the final results at country level since the range of variability in the reservoirs' areas is much larger. There are many important factors to consider when developing new hydropower plants, which are not

Table 5

Energy and energy related water consumption profiles for the 36 countries with hydropower plants analysed in this study. Main results for hydropower and the sum of other energy types (fossil fuels, non-hydro renewable energies, nuclear and waste heat) analysed in this study are presented for each country (ordered by WL).

Country	Hydropower					Total Non-Hydro energies				
	IC (GW)	EP (GWh)	WL (mcm)	N	% TIC	RA (km ²)	WL/EP (mcm/GWh)	IC (GW)	EP (GWh)	WC (mcm)
GHANA	1.61	5638	9524.63	3	100%	6004.73	1.69	2.15	8387	4.10
EGYPT	2.69	12,790	5757.43	2	95%	5248.37	0.45	35.87	172,111	174.58
ZAMBIA	2.20	10,143	5626.23	6	94%	3387.15	0.55	0.29	465	1.58
MOZAMBIQUE	2.18	15,580	4421.75	4	100%	2391.20	0.28	0.68	3178	3.10
ZIMBABWE	0.68	2296	3105.37	1	96%	1862.29	1.35	1.43	4161	8.95
NIGERIA	1.97	7601	2881.69	4	99%	1815.36	0.38	13.84	31,113	71.72
SUDAN	1.59	8043	2718.96	5	100%	1966.50	0.34	2.46	6708	31.12
COTE D'IVOIRE	0.62	1564	1738.42	6	100%	1240.85	1.11	1.34	7608	6.30
CAMEROON	0.75	4504	1065.80	3	100%	610.02	0.24	0.54	3753	4.13
TANZANIA	0.57	2401	1024.10	7	98%	613.08	0.43	1.37	4706	1.21
ETHIOPIA	2.42	10,834	923.27	9	84%	796.06	0.09	0.68	830	0.09
CONGO D.R.	1.32	4799	640.46	8	90%	401.51	0.13	0.05	14	0.80
MALI	0.32	1891	618.44	3	98%	826.80	0.33	0.39	861	0.20
MOROCCO	1.76	1649	439.38	22	99%	408.94	0.27	6.49	29,989	5.33
BURK. FASO	0.03	146	419.88	2	93%	353.84	2.88	0.37	835	0.16
SOUTH AFRICA	2.93	3561	302.14	13	99%	449.26	0.08	49.08	249,164	508.81
ANGOLA	1.18	4381	301.80	8	99%	201.02	0.07	1.20	4546	8.46
TOGO	0.07	201	204.82	1	97%	138.84	1.02	0.24	23	0.00
KENYA	0.75	3234	182.03	7	92%	180.27	0.06	1.81	6692	3.13
GUINEA	0.34	1014	151.75	4	94%	109.13	0.15	0.38	512	0.27
CONGO	0.19	1126	78.11	2	100%	53.51	0.07	0.41	794	3.45
GABON	0.29	1380	34.94	3	86%	27.69	0.03	0.31	711	15.57
MADAGASCAR	0.10	549	16.94	4	75%	26.46	0.03	0.50	908	0.52
SIERRA LEONE	0.06	219	13.89	2	97%	10.03	0.06	0.21	85	0.01
ALGERIA	0.24	76	11.82	7	87%	36.55	0.16	19.62	73,073	262.72
TUNISIA	0.06	38	10.17	3	90%	39.10	0.27	5.04	20,767	8.63
NAMIBIA	0.35	1567	8.43	1	100%	5.16	0.01	0.20	91	4.79
MAURITIUS	0.04	68	3.65	2	68%	3.28	0.05	0.83	3333	1.59
RWANDA	0.03	86	3.47	1	35%	3.26	0.04	0.10	341	0.07
MALAWI	0.34	1904	2.79	3	99%	1.92	0.00	0.08	256	0.21
ESWATINI	0.06	124	2.37	4	97%	6.49	0.02	0.11	205	0.49
UGANDA	0.67	3169	1.88	5	95%	1.32	0.00	0.337	415	0.41
BURUNDI	0.02	96	1.72	1	51%	1.53	0.02	0.006	24	0.00
EQ. GUINEA	0.12	121	0.98	1	94%	0.85	0.01	0.185	542	1.21
LESOTHO	0.07	502	0.20	1	94%	0.18	0.00	0.002	0	0.00
C. AFR. REP.	0.02	134	0.02	1	99%	0.01	0.00	0.007	1	0.00

IC: installed capacity.

EP: energy production.

WL: water loss through evaporation in hydropower reservoirs.

N: number of reservoirs included in the study.

% TIC: % of total hydropower installed capacity covered by the study.

RA: reservoirs' combined area in the country.

WC: water consumption from non-hydro energies.

discussed in this study. From the point of view of reducing the water loss through evaporation, it is key to decrease the reservoir's area, in which topography has an important role. For instance, a valley-shaped topography with an adequate slope of the surrounding terrain that allows to obtain the target hydraulic head with the minimum reservoir surface, would become an ideal location for a hydropower development in this context. In these cases, higher installed capacities could be achieved with smaller reservoir areas, given an adequate availability of water flow. We can take some examples from the reservoirs analysed in the study to illustrate this fact. For instance, Al Massira and Bine El Ouidane dams, both located in Morocco, present very similar installed capacities (139 MW and 135 MW respectively) and are located in regions with similar evaporation rates. However, Al Massira dam, located in a relatively flat valley with a dam height of 82 m [39], has a reservoir area more than three times larger than Bine El Ouidane, located in the Atlas Mountains with a dam height of 133 m [39]. The water loss in al Massira is 3.6 times larger than the water loss in Bine El Ouidane. Other cases that illustrate the importance of reducing the reservoirs' area are for example Imboulou (Congo) and Allal el Fassi (Morocco), which account only for 14% and 3% of the water loss of Itzhi Tezhi (Zambia) and Al Wahda (Morocco) respectively, due to much smaller reservoir areas, having both the same installed capacities and similar evaporation rates. Identifying locations with lower evaporation rates would also

be important to reduce water loss, although the evaporation rate may present less variability within a given country compared to the effect that can be achieved by reducing the reservoirs' areas.

It is interesting to note that four of the countries with the highest water loss (Egypt, Zambia, Ghana and Zimbabwe) present values in 2016 close to the minimum observed for the period 2000–2018 (Fig. 16). This means that in the last two decades, these countries have experienced water losses even much larger than the results presented in this study. At reservoir level, in 2016, 35% of all reservoirs (including large reservoirs such as Akosombo, Aswan High, and Kariba) presented values of water loss below the mean of the period 2000–2018. An uncertainty analysis regarding the period 2000–2018 is added in the [supplementary material](#). Confidence intervals are also produced for water loss estimates at the county level to illustrate the impact of sampling uncertainty.

The efficiency of a hydropower reservoir in terms of water loss by evaporation in relation to the installed capacity or electricity production is the result of the combination of a number of factors such as the area of reservoirs, climate, terrain, installed capacity, capacity factors and allocation of shared uses. Fig. 17 provides a general overview of the density of power plants in Africa (first row) considering also the installed capacity and water consumption (second and third row). For instance, while there are two high density areas located in east and west

Fig. 16. Hydropower installed capacity and water loss from hydropower plants for the countries with highest water losses for the year 2016 (ordered by installed capacity). The bars indicate the range (maximum and minimum values) of water loss during the period 2000–2018.

* Density of plants: the maps were created using the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) algorithm based on the quartic kernel shape. Weights were applied in the second and third rows to visualize the density of plants when considering the installed capacity and water consumption.

Fig. 17. Distribution maps for different types of power plants (fossil fuels, hydropower and non-hydro renewable energies). Row 1: power plant density; Row 2: power plant density weighted by installed capacity; Row 3: power plant density weighted by water consumption.

Fig. 18. Total water consumption for all energy types (excluding fuelwood) and the associated water consumption per capita for the top 25 countries with highest water consumption (ordered by total water consumption).

Africa, these plants are not of very high installed capacities (second row). However, the maps in the third row show an important water consumption in those areas due to the presence of hydropower plants. This figure clearly shows the impact of hydropower in the total water consumption for energy production, in which other fuel types have a marginal contribution in comparison despite having higher densities of plants and installed capacities. The impact of other non-hydro renewable energies is almost negligible in this context.

One last aspect to look at in this analysis is how water-intensive is the energy sector in relation to the population [51]. The total water consumption of all energy types (including hydropower) compared with its values per capita at country level is shown in Fig. 18. Egypt and Zambia for instance, have similar total water consumption, however, Egypt shows a significantly lower consumption of water for energy production per capita due to a larger population. A similar behaviour can be observed between Zimbabwe and Nigeria. In these cases, it is interesting to note that despite the much higher use of water for energy production per capita in Zimbabwe and Zambia, the population with access to electricity in these two countries is almost half of the one in Nigeria and one third of Egypt respectively [76].

Water for hydropower plant construction was also considered in this analysis, however this component is negligible compared to the water loss by evaporation in the reservoirs (water factors in Table 4) and therefore it is not discussed in this study.

3.7. Previous studies

The results of this research are compared with a number of previous studies from the literature. These studies differ in terms of scope (energy processes included, type of water analysed, etc), time frame, and geographical coverage. For instance, [13,77] consider both freshwater and seawater as water use and [14,77–79] do not include hydropower in their analyses. Furthermore, while all of these studies perform a global scale analysis, some of them focus only on water use for cooling of thermal power plants. On the other hand, water use allocated to fuelwood production is not addressed by any of them. The number of studies in the literature addressing water use for energy production in

Africa is also significantly more limited than for other regions. Results in [13] for the period 2008–2012 in Africa, show a yearly water consumption of 1007 mcm for primary energy production, 2.2 mcm for power plant construction and 54,888 mcm for power plant operations including hydropower. These estimations show a good alignment with the results presented in this study and the differences may arise from the fact that in [13], all power plants are assumed to use freshwater for cooling. The total water consumption in South Africa, Angola, Nigeria and Algeria obtained in [14] seem also to fit well with our estimates at country level. Regarding water use for cooling of thermal plants, [77,79] obtained values of 612 mcm (2015) and 449 mcm (2010) respectively, showing consistency with the results in this study (502 mcm for 2016).

Previous studies focusing exclusively on water loss through evaporation from reservoirs [35,36] are also evaluated for comparison at reservoir level, since they analyse some of the reservoirs included in this study. However, the results are difficult to compare since the extension of the reservoirs, the time reference, the method to obtain the evaporation rate and the shared uses allocation methodology can differ significantly from one study to another. The main difference comes from the areas of the reservoirs, obtained from published datasets in the two studies [35,36], while we used GSW data derived from satellite imagery. The methodologies to obtain the evaporation rates are also different, leading for instance to significant discrepancies between our study and [35], in which the evaporation rates are up to 42% higher for the reservoirs compared. The evaporation rates presented in [36] are more similar to the ones used in our study. However, in this case the discrepancies arise from the use of a correction factor in the reservoir areas without which the final water losses for the reservoirs compared seem to be in line with our results.

4. Discussion

Freshwater use in the current fossil fuels-based energy sector can be reduced in a number of ways. A wider use of natural gas or salt/reclaimed water for oil extraction would decrease significantly the freshwater use for fuel extraction. More efficient plants using an appropriate cooling system adapted to the local water resources and climate would also contribute substantially. In this case, the trade-off between withdrawals and consumption needs to be considered. The current trends that switch from open-cycle to close-cycle or dry cooling systems help to alleviate the environmental impacts caused by the first, however the increase in cost and water consumption are factors that need to be taken into account. Data availability is often a challenge when addressing Africa. Additionally, due to lack of data, global average water factors are normally used when analysing the water use of energy, involving also a number of assumptions. Electricity production at plant level and country/region-specific water factors could further improve the accuracy and reliability of the results.

Africa presents the highest untapped technical hydropower potential in the world having developed only 11% of the total [80]. While hydropower can questionably be considered a low-carbon technology considering the important amounts of carbon dioxide and methane that can emit due to decomposing vegetation under the water [81], it is certainly a very important consumer of water. Climate in terms of evaporation and water availability needs also to be considered when selecting sites for new hydropower developments. Further research could focus on the estimation of the net water losses from the hydropower reservoirs analysed in this study. This may result in lower values of water loss allocated to the presence of the dam due to the natural evaporation of the river before the plant construction. Identifying accurately the starting point of the reservoir in the river is also a difficulty often faced in these types of studies and for which more advanced techniques could be further developed. The seasonal variation of the reservoirs over time could also be investigated and further analyses could be performed in order to forecast periods of water scarcity based

on the historic Global Surface Water time series. Complex methodologies for shared uses allocation can be further developed, integrating several aspects such as priority of uses, regulations and economic and social valuations. The methodology presented in this study can be extended to other regions and applied at different scales not only to determine the water loss through evaporation in existing reservoirs but also to evaluate the possible impacts of a future development.

5. Conclusion

The present study provides reliable estimates of the energy sector's water consumption and withdrawal in the African continent. The processes analysed are fuel production (extraction and processing), power plant construction and operation. The hydropower context in Africa is highly complex and an in-depth analysis of water loss through evaporation from hydropower plants was required and carried out in this work.

Water consumption for fuel production is dominated by oil with the highest water factors (for extraction and refining) among all fuel types. On the other hand, water consumption associated to natural gas is minimal for all countries in Africa despite being the second fuel type after oil regarding production, due to a less water-intensive extraction process. Fuelwood has proved to be a high consumer of water due to an important reliance on wood in households for cooking and heating purposes, mainly in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Regarding power plant operation, results indicate that water loss by evaporation from hydropower reservoirs is in general several orders of magnitude larger than the total water consumption by all other types of fuels combined. The total water loss through evaporation allocated to hydropower production in Africa in the year 2016 exceeds 42 billion cubic meters (equivalent to more than 80% of the total water volume of Cahora Bassa [39], the fourth largest hydropower reservoir in Africa). The size of the reservoirs, climate and allocation of shared uses are the key factors that determine the water loss associated with hydropower. Countries counting with more numerous but smaller reservoirs show generally less water loss than countries relying on big reservoirs for similar installed capacities. Cooling of fossil fuel power plants dominates the rest of the water consumption and withdrawal depending highly on the type of cooling system installed. While natural gas is the fuel with the highest installed capacity in Africa, it only contributes minimally to the total water consumption for power plant operation, but accounts for a dominant share to water withdrawal. Coal power plants, on the other hand, show an opposite behaviour with high water consumption and minimal water withdrawal. Water use for power plant construction shows to be relatively marginal and only significant in the case of renewable energies. The water consumption related to non-hydro renewable energies is almost negligible compared to other types of energies.

The growing energy demand in Africa presents an interesting opportunity to develop the energy sector in more sustainable ways, not only aiming towards decarbonisation but also towards water savings. Non-hydro renewable energies have proven to be substantially less water-intensive technologies than fossil fuels and the lowest overall. Further development in this direction is highly recommended in order to reduce drastically the water use for energy. The African continent has a significant renewable energy potential that remains mostly untapped, especially for solar and wind energy. Each of the five regions in Africa present inherent differences that require adopting different development strategies, but also provides interesting opportunities for interconnection among the power pools. The cost of the development of these energy sources has been a deterrent in the past. However, this cost has been decreasing steadily and these technologies are at the point where they are economically feasible and fairly competitive with conventional sources.

Power grid infrastructure is one of the obstacles that renewable energies have to face in Africa, especially in the sub-Saharan region.

Although the solar and wind potential can be high in many regions, the countries may have to invest not only in the development of the new plant but also in grid extensions. Future research efforts should focus on approaches to enhance energy generation from existing infrastructure in different regions of the African continent. This also includes retrofitting non-powered dams that meet certain criteria in order to produce electricity. The installation of floating solar panels on the surface of the reservoirs is another option that can aid at the same time to reduce evaporation from reservoirs especially in hot regions of Africa. The transition from traditional use of biomass in low efficiency appliances to modern bioenergy systems with higher efficiency could decrease biomass demand, reducing water consumption and deforestation. It is also important to assess the future renewable energies potential in Africa under climatic change conditions, and to model the evolution of the availability of fossil fuels in different regions of the continent. This is necessary to ensure a rational and stable transition in the energy mix in the continent and to safeguard the optimal integration of renewable energies. Finally, it is important to look in detail at the existing socio-economic barriers to the development of renewables that are specific to the African continent. Issues related to intelligent financing and local capacity building need also to be addressed to ensure the long-term sustainability of these sources and the universal access to electricity in the continent.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Rocio Gonzalez Sanchez: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft. **Roman Seliger:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft, Software. **Fernando Fahl:** Visualization. **Luca De Felice:** Software. **Taha B.M.J. Ouarda:** Writing - review & editing. **Fabio Farinosi:** Formal analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Ignacio Hidalgo Gonzalez, Ioannis Kougiass, Nicolae Scarlat, Hrvoje Medarac, Christian Thiel and Cesar Carmona Moreno (Joint Research Centre - European Commission) for providing valuable insights. The authors would also like to thank Prof. J. Yan, Editor-in-chief, and the three anonymous reviewers for their comments which helped improve the quality of the manuscript.

Disclaimer

The views expressed are purely those of the authors and may not in any circumstances be regarded as stating an official position of the European Commission.

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115171>.

References

- [1] IEA. World energy outlook 2016. OECD; 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1787/weo-2016-en>.
- [2] EEA. Water use by sectors. 2018. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/archived/archived-content-water-topic/water-resources/water-use-by-sectors> [accessed June 20, 2018].
- [3] Dieter CA, Maupin MA, Caldwell RR, Harris MA, Ivahnenko TI, Lovelace JK, et al. Estimated use of water in the United States in 2015. Reston, VA: 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2018.05.010>.

- [org/10.3133/cir1441](https://doi.org/10.3133/cir1441).
- [4] UNCCD. Desertification. The invisible frontline; 2014.
 - [5] UN Water. Coping with water scarcity. Challenge of the twenty-first century; 2007.
 - [6] Meldrum J, Nettles-Anderson S, Heath G, Macknick J. Life cycle water use for electricity generation: a review and harmonization of literature estimates. *Environ Res Lett* 2013;8:15031.
 - [7] Ali B, Kumar A. Development of life cycle water-demand coefficients for coal-based power generation technologies. *Energy Convers Manag* 2015;90:247–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2014.11.013>.
 - [8] Ali B, Kumar A. Development of water demand coefficients for power generation from renewable energy technologies. *Energy Convers Manag* 2017;143:470–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.04.028>.
 - [9] Ou Y, Zhai H, Rubin ES. Life cycle water use of coal- and natural-gas-fired power plants with and without carbon capture and storage. *Int J Greenh Gas Control* 2016;44:249–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2015.11.029>.
 - [10] Macknick J, Newmark R, Heath G, Hallett KC. Operational water consumption and withdrawal factors for electricity generating technologies: a review of existing literature. *Environ Res Lett* 2012;7:45802.
 - [11] Liao X, Hall JW, Eyre N. Water use in China's thermoelectric power sector. *Glob Environ Chang* 2016;41:142–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.09.007>.
 - [12] Lee U, Han J, Elgowainy A, Wang M. Regional water consumption for hydro and thermal electricity generation in the United States. *Appl Energy* 2018;210:661–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.05.025>.
 - [13] Mekonnen MM, Gerbens-Leenes PW, Hoekstra AY. The consumptive water footprint of electricity and heat: a global assessment. *Environ Sci Water Res Technol* 2015;1:285–97. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5EW00026B>.
 - [14] Spang ES, Moomaw WR, Gallagher KS, Kirshen PH, Marks DH. The water consumption of energy production: an international comparison. *Environ Res Lett* 2014;9:105002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/9/10/105002>.
 - [15] Zheng X, Wang C, Cai W, Kummu M, Varis O. The vulnerability of thermoelectric power generation to water scarcity in China: Current status and future scenarios for power planning and climate change. *Appl Energy* 2016;171:444–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.03.040>.
 - [16] Srinivasan S, Kholod N, Chaturvedi V, Ghosh PP, Mathur R, Clarke L, et al. Water for electricity in India: A multi-model study of future challenges and linkages to climate change mitigation. *Appl Energy* 2018;210:673–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.04.079>.
 - [17] Kenny JF, Barber NL, Hutson SS, Linsey KS, Lovelace JK, Maupin MA. Estimated use of water in the United States in 2005. *US Geol Survey* 2009.
 - [18] Schneider E, Carlsen B, Tavriles E, van der Hoeven C, Phathanapirom U. Measures of the environmental footprint of the front end of the nuclear fuel cycle. *Energy Econ* 2013;40:898–910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2013.01.002>.
 - [19] EPRI. Comparison of alternate cooling technologies for California power plants economic, environmental and other tradeoffs. Citeseer; 2002.
 - [20] Peer RAM, Sanders KT. The water consequences of a transitioning US power sector. *Appl Energy* 2018;210:613–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.08.021>.
 - [21] Fleischli S, Hayat B. Power plant cooling and associated impacts: the need to modernize US power plants and protect our water resources and aquatic ecosystems; 2014.
 - [22] Madden N, Lewis A, Davis M. Thermal effluent from the power sector: an analysis of once-through cooling system impacts on surface water temperature. *Environ Res Lett* 2013;8:35006.
 - [23] IEA. World energy outlook; 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1787/weo-2014-en>.
 - [24] IEA. World energy balances; 2018. https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/energy/data/iea-world-energy-statistics-and-balances/world-energy-balances_data-00512-en [accessed September 15, 2018].
 - [25] S&P Global Platts. World electric power plants database; 2016. <https://www.platts.com/products/world-electric-power-plants-database>.
 - [26] BP. Energy outlook. Africa; 2017. <https://www.bp.com/en/global/corporate/energy-economics/energy-outlook.html>.
 - [27] FAO. Irrigation in Africa in figures. AQUASTAT Survey 2005;29.
 - [28] UN Water. Water for life decade; 2014. <https://www.un.org/waterforlifedecade/africa.shtml> [accessed May 25, 2018].
 - [29] FAO. Water for agriculture and energy in Africa. The challenges of climate change; 2008.
 - [30] VOA news. DRC faces power shortage caused by drought; 2017. <https://www.voanews.com/africa/drc-faces-power-shortage-caused-drought> [accessed June 30, 2018].
 - [31] Reuters. Zimbabwe's main hydro power dam running out of water after drought; 2016. <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-zimbabwe-drought-powerstation/zimbabwes-main-hydro-power-dam-running-out-of-water-after-drought-idUSKCN0V51GM> [accessed June 30, 2018].
 - [32] The Guardian. Malawi suffers blackouts as drought exposes 98% reliance on hydro power; 2017. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2017/dec/08/malawi-blackouts-drought-hydro-power> [accessed June 30, 2018].
 - [33] Loisulie S. Vulnerability of Tanzania hydropower production to extreme weather events. *Jt. ICTP-IAEA Work. Vulnerability Energy Syst. to Clim. Chang. Extrem. Events*; 2010.
 - [34] Gleick PH. Water and energy. *Annu Rev Energy Environ* 1994;19:267–99. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.eg.19.110194.001411>.
 - [35] Mekonnen MM, Hoekstra AY. The blue water footprint of electricity from hydropower. *Hydrol Earth Syst Sci* 2012;16:179–87. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-16-179-2012>.
 - [36] Hogeboom RJ, Knook L, Hoekstra AY. The blue water footprint of the world's artificial reservoirs for hydroelectricity, irrigation, residential and industrial water supply, flood protection, fishing and recreation. *Adv Water Resour* 2018;113:285–94.
 - [37] Scherer L, Pfister S. Global water footprint assessment of hydropower. *Renew Energy* 2016;99:711–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2016.07.021>.
 - [38] ICOLD. World Register of Dams (WRD); 2013. https://www.icold-cigb.org/GB/world_register/world_register_of_dams.asp.
 - [39] Lehner B, Liermann CR, Revenga C, Vörösmarty C, Fekete B, Crouzet P, et al. High-resolution mapping of the world's reservoirs and dams for sustainable river-flow management. *Front Ecol Environ* 2011;9:494–502. <https://doi.org/10.1890/100125>.
 - [40] Zhao D, Liu J. A new approach to assessing the water footprint of hydroelectric power based on allocation of water footprints among reservoir ecosystem services. *Phys Chem Earth, Parts A/B/C* 2015;79–82:40–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2015.03.005>.
 - [41] Bakken TH, Modahl IS, Engeland K, Raadal HL, Arnøy S. The life-cycle water footprint of two hydropower projects in Norway. *J Clean Prod* 2016;113:241–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.12.036>.
 - [42] Coelho CD, da Silva DD, Sediya GC, Moreira MC, Pereira SB, Lana ÂMQ. Comparison of the water footprint of two hydropower plants in the Tocantins River Basin of Brazil. *J Clean Prod* 2017;153:164–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.03.088>.
 - [43] Busker T, De Roo A, Gelati E, Schwatke C, Adamovic M, Bisselink B, et al. A global lake and reservoir volume analysis using a surface water dataset and satellite altimetry. *Hydrol Earth Syst Sci* 2019;23:669–90. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-23-669-2019>.
 - [44] Herath I, Deurer M, Horne D, Singh R, Clothier B. The water footprint of hydroelectricity: A methodological comparison from a case study in New Zealand. *J Clean Prod* 2011;19:1582–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.05.007>.
 - [45] AFREC. Africa energy database; 2017. <https://africa-energy-portal.org/database> [accessed September 5, 2018].
 - [46] Rystad Energy. UCUBE; 2018. <https://www.rystadenergy.com/products/EnP-Solutions/ucube/>.
 - [47] Wu M, Chiu Y. Consumptive water use in the production of ethanol and petroleum gasoline-2011 update. *Cent Transp Res* 2011.
 - [48] WNA. Uranium country profiles; 2019. <https://www.world-nuclear.org/information-library/country-profiles.aspx> [accessed September 23, 2018].
 - [49] Tinto R. Rossing Uranium. Report to stakeholders; 2017.
 - [50] Paladin Energy LTD. Sustainability report. ACN061681098; 2016.
 - [51] UN. UN data; 2016. <http://data.un.org/> [accessed April 5, 2018].
 - [52] Schyns JF, Booi MJ, Hoekstra AY. The water footprint of wood for lumber, pulp, paper, fuel and firewood. *Adv Water Resour* 2017;107:490–501. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2017.05.013>.
 - [53] Google. Google Earth Pro; 2019. <https://www.google.com/earth/>.
 - [54] Harvard. Africa power plants; 2010. http://worldmap.harvard.edu/data/geonode:africa_power_plants_gd4.
 - [55] Energydata.info. Africa – Power stations; 2012. <https://energydata.info/en/dataset/africa-power-stations-2012>.
 - [56] WRI. Global power plants database; 2018. <https://www.wri.org/publication/global-power-plant-database>.
 - [57] IRENA. Renewable capacity statistics. Abu Dhabi: Int Renew Energy Agency (IRENA); 2018.
 - [58] Zhang C, Zhong L, Fu X, Wang J, Wu Z. Revealing water stress by the thermal power industry in China based on a high spatial resolution water withdrawal and consumption inventory. *Environ Sci Technol* 2016;50:1642–52. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b05374>.
 - [59] Medarac H, Magagna D, Hidalgo Gonzalez I. Projected fresh water use from the European energy sector; 2018. <https://doi.org/10.2760/30414>.
 - [60] EIA. Average tested heat rates by prime mover and energy source (2007– 2017); 2017. https://www.eia.gov/electricity/annual/html/epa_08_02.html [accessed August 7, 2018].
 - [61] Jäger-Waldau A. PV status report 2017. EUR 28817 EN, Publ Off Eur Union, Luxemb; 2017. ISBN 978-92-79-74071-8, Doi102760/452611, JRC108105; 2018.
 - [62] Pekel JF, Cottam A, Gorelick N, Belward AS. High-resolution mapping of global surface water and its long-term changes. *Nature* 2016;540:418–22. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature20584>.
 - [63] EC JRC/Google. JRC monthly water history, v1.1; n.d. https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/JRC_GSW1_1_MonthlyHistory [accessed October 1, 2019].
 - [64] EC JRC/Google. JRC yearly water classification history, V.1.1; n.d. https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/JRC_GSW1_1_YearlyHistory [accessed October 5, 2019].
 - [65] Cordano E. Estimation of wet season duration in a year; 2018. <https://aquaknow.jrc.ec.europa.eu/acewater2-jrc/dataset/estimation-wet-season-duration-year> [accessed August 7, 2019].
 - [66] Funk C, Peterson P, Landsfeld M, Pedreros D, Verdin J, Shukla S, et al. The climate hazards infrared precipitation with stations - a new environmental record for monitoring extremes. *Sci Data* 2015;2:150066. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2015.66>.
 - [67] Gorelick N, Hancher M, Dixon M, Ilyushchenko S, Thau D, Moore R. Google Earth Engine: Planetary-scale geospatial analysis for everyone. *Remote Sens Environ* 2017.
 - [68] OpenStreetMap. OpenStreetMap; 2019. openstreetmap.org.
 - [69] FAO. Evaporation from artificial lakes and reservoirs. FAO AQUASTAT; 2015.
 - [70] Burek PA, Van Der Knijff J, Ntegeka VN. LISVAP evaporation pre-processor for the LISFLOOD water balance and flood simulation model; 2013.
 - [71] Alfieri L, Lorini V, Hirpa FA, Harrigan S, Zsoter E, Prudhomme C, et al. A global streamflow reanalysis for 1980–2018. *J Hydrol X* 2020;6:100049. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hydroa.2019.100049>.
 - [72] Copernicus Climate Change Service. ERA5: Fifth generation of ECMWF atmospheric reanalyses of the global climate. Copernicus Clim Chang Serv Clim Data Store; 2017. <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!home> [accessed August 12, 2019].
 - [73] FAO. Geo-referenced database on dams in Africa. Notes and References. AQUASTAT; 2016.

- [74] Bakken TH, Killingtveit Å, Alfredsen K. The water footprint of hydropower production-state of the art and methodological challenges. *Glob Challenges* 2017;1:1600018. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.201600018>.
- [75] IEA. Energy access outlook; 2017. From poverty to prosperity.
- [76] IEA. Access to electricity. SDG7 Data Proj; 2019. <https://www.iea.org/reports/sdg7-data-and-projections/access-to-electricity> [accessed October 6, 2019].
- [77] Lohrmann A, Farfan J, Caldera U, Lohrmann C, Breyer C. Global scenarios for significant water use reduction in thermal power plants based on cooling water demand estimation using satellite imagery. *Nat Energy* 2019;4:1040–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-019-0501-4>.
- [78] Vassolo S, Döll P. Global-scale gridded estimates of thermoelectric power and manufacturing water use. *Water Resour Res* 2005;41. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004WR003360>.
- [79] Flörke M, Teichert E, Bärlund I, Eisner S, Wimmer F, Alcamo J. Domestic and industrial water uses of the past 60 years as a mirror of socio-economic development: A global simulation study. *Glob Environ Chang* 2013;23:144–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2012.10.018>.
- [80] IHA. Hydropower status report. Int Hydropower Assoc; 2018.
- [81] Fearnside PM. Hydroelectric dams in the Brazilian Amazon as sources of 'Greenhouse' gases. *Environ Conserv* 1995;22:7–19. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892900034020>.